

SYNTHESIS OF SOME SUBSTITUTED SULPHATHIAZOLES

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Seven different substituted 2-aminothiazoles have been prepared and condensed with acetylsulphanilyl chloride to obtain the corresponding sulphonamides in order to study their therapeutic activity.

Investigations for the synthesis of compounds related to sulphanilamide and for the study of their chemotherapeutic properties, with a view to overcoming some of the drawbacks of the drugs so far known (Goodman and Levy, *J. Amer. Med. Assoc.*, 1937, 109, 1005; Bucy, *ibid.*, 1937, 109, 1007), comprised mainly replacement of the amido-H by some other chain or group, mostly heterocyclic moiety. These led to the discovery of sulphathiazole, sulphadiazine and sulphaguanidine. That such replacements are expected to have a great therapeutic importance has also been stressed by several workers (Whitely, *Lancet*, 1937, i, 1517; Crossbey *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2217).

In view of the usefulness of the thiazole compounds in therapy (Barnbas, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 671; Schaeffer and Toomey, *Amer. J. Med.*, 1945, 6, 667; Bovet *et al.*, *Amer. Inst. Pasteur*, 1946, 72, 105; Sondern and Breivogel, U.S.P. 2440703/1948), the authors considered worthwhile to undertake the preparation of substituted sulphathiazoles as a systematic study involving variation of substituents on the thiazolyl nucleus does not seem to have been undertaken.

The substituted 2-aminothiazoles were prepared from substituted hydroxyacetophenones, viz., 2-hydroxy-(5-methyl-, 4-methyl-, 4-ethyl-, 3-chloro-, 3:5-dichloro- and 3-chloro-4-methyl)-acetophenones, by treating with thiourea in the presence of iodine, following the method of King and Hlavacek (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 3722).

The required ketones were obtained by the Fries migration of the acetates of the corresponding phenols in the usual way. The acetates were prepared by following the method of Chattaway (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2495).

*The condensation of 2-aminothiazoles with acetylsulphanilyl chloride in pyridine (cf. Das and Rout, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 663) yielded the substituted 2-acetamid sulphonamides, which were also hydrolysed to the corresponding 2-amino compounds with 12% hydrochloric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Amino-4-p-chlorophenyl-5-methylthiazole.—A mixture of *p*-chloropropiophenone (8.4 g.), thiourea (7.6 g.) and iodine (12.7 g.) was heated for 24 hours on the steam-bath, then cooled and extracted with ether to remove the unchanged ketone and iodine. The residue was extracted with boiling water and filtered. Ammonia was added to the filtrate and the solid separating was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 140°, yield 55%. (Found: S, 13.87. $C_{10}H_9N_2ClS$ requires S, 14.25%).

The other six thiazoles were prepared in the same way from the appropriate hydroxyacetophenones and were characterised through their acetyl derivatives, prepared in the usual way. The m.p., yields and analysis of the substituted 2-aminothiazoles and their acetyl derivatives are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

	2-Aminothiazole.				Acetates		
	M.P.	% Yield.	% Sulphur.		M.P.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Calc.		Found.	Calc.
4- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl-5-methyl-A	140°	55	13.87	14.25	235°	11.63	12.00
4-(2-Hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-A	200°	46	15.21	15.53	216°	12.67	12.91
4-(2-Hydroxy-4-methylphenyl)-A	175°	42	15.23	15.53	195°	12.73	12.91
4-(2-Hydroxy-4-ethylphenyl)-A	132°	52	14.23	14.54	153°	11.87	12.21
4-(2-Hydroxy-3-chlorophenyl)-A	207°	39	13.86	14.21	241°	11.67	11.91
4-(2-Hydroxy-3:5-dichlorophenyl)-A	117°	25	12.03	12.26	..	..	..
4-(2-Hydroxy-3-chloro-4-methylphenyl)-A	185°	48	12.95	13.30	261°	11.21	11.32

N.B. A denotes 2-aminothiazole.

4-*p*-Chlorophenyl-5-methyl-2-(N⁴-acetylsulphanilamido)-thiazole.—4-*p*-Chlorophenyl-5-methyl-2-aminothiazole (1.9 g.) and *p*-acetamidobenzenesulphonyl chloride (2.3 g.) were treated with freshly distilled pyridine (15 c.c.). The mixture was heated on a water-bath at 65-70° for 2½ hours. After cooling, the mixture was diluted with water, when a precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed with water, and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 295°, yield 58%. (Found: N, 9.58. C₁₈H₁₆O₃N₃ClS₂ requires N, 9.96%).

4-*p*-Chlorophenyl-5-methyl-2-sulphanilamidothiazole.—To the above compound (1 g.) 12% HCl (4 c.c.) was added and the mixture slowly refluxed for 2 hours. It was then poured into a beaker containing an equal volume of water, heated to boiling and filtered. The filtrate was cooled and solid sodium carbonate was added in small portions with continuous stirring until the solution was just alkaline to litmus. The precipitate formed was filtered, washed and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 162° (decomp.), yield 30%. (Found: N, 10.95. C₁₈H₁₄O₂N₃ClS₂ requires N, 11.32%).

The m. p., yields and analytical data for the condensation products of *p*-acetamidobenzenesulphonyl chloride with other 2-aminothiazoles, and their corresponding amino compounds are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

R ₁ .	$\begin{array}{c} \text{R}_1\text{-C} \text{---} \text{N} \\ \parallel \quad \parallel \\ \text{R}_2\text{-C} \quad \text{C-NHSO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NHCOMe} \\ \diagdown \quad / \\ \text{S} \end{array}$					$\begin{array}{c} \text{R}_1\text{-C} \text{---} \text{N} \\ \parallel \quad \parallel \\ \text{R}_2\text{-C} \quad \text{C-NHSO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2 \\ \diagdown \quad / \\ \text{S} \end{array}$			
	R ₂ .	M.P.	% Yield.	% Nitrogen. Found.	Calc.	M.P.	% Yield.	% Nitrogen. Found.	Calc.
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl-	Me	296°	58	9.58	9.96	162°	30	10.95	11.33
2-Hydroxy-5-methylphenyl-	H	200°	50	10.13	10.42	..	..	..	..
2-Hydroxy-4-methylphenyl-	H	250°	56	10.07	10.42	189°	40	11.07	11.64
2-Hydroxy-4-ethylphenyl-	H	152°	55	9.83	10.07	144°	45	11.16	11.30
2-Hydroxy-3-chlorophenyl-	H	195°	58	9.34	9.91	..	..	..	..
2-Hydroxy-3:5-dichlorophenyl-	H	93°	45	8.89	9.17	..	..	..	..
2-Hydroxy-3-chloro-4-methylphenyl-	H	165°	48	9.47	9.66	148°	35	10.32	10.60